

Training needs, skills and awareness of existing resources among PhD students

A report on the project "Identifying PhD students' training needs" conducted by DARIAH Working Group Community Engagement

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1. Introduction

The use of digital tools, methods, and content is increasingly common among researchers in the Arts and Humanities field. To foster greater participation, raise awareness, and encourage innovative use of the extensive digitized research data in Europe and beyond, as well as to promote research infrastructures, the most effective approach is to provide support for communities of researchers. In line with this goal, the DARIAH-EU Working Group Community Engagement was established in 2014 to facilitate community building. The group aims to support collaboration, knowledge exchange, and idea-sharing among researchers. We firmly believe that researchers can learn most effectively from each other, express their needs, and together explore new pathways for advancing research.

In late 2021, DARIAH initiated the third Working Groups (WG) Funding Scheme Call for the period from 2021 to 2023. This exclusive scheme is specifically designed for the DARIAH Working Groups, aiming to provide assistance for their activities, small-scale projects, and the advancement or continuity of innovative ideas.

The WG Community Engagement was awarded funding for a small project on the identification of Digital Humanities training needs of PhD students coming from different disciplines and varying expertise levels. Given the diversity within the DH field, the training requirements for PhD students entering from different backgrounds also varied. To explore this systematically, the project delved into the wealth of training and educational tools and resources provided by DARIAH.

One of the key outputs of the project was a survey tailored for PhD students who were working with DH tools and engaged with DARIAH communities. The survey adhered to established ethics and data protection guidelines, drawing inspiration from the Web Archives Researcher Skills and Tools Survey (WARST)¹. Through this survey, the project documented and analyzed the participants' training needs, skills, and awareness of existing resources.

To reach potential participants, the project utilized existing DARIAH channels like newsletters and social media, as well as the personal networks of the working group members. In the next phase, a representative focus group of respondents was invited to attend an in-person workshop in Mainz. During this workshop, in-depth focus group interviews were conducted, and participants collaboratively evaluated existing training materials. These interviews offered valuable insights into the specific training needs of researchers at this stage of their careers.

The insights gathered from both the survey and the workshop will be compiled into a comprehensive report. This report will be shared with DARIAH's research and education officer, as well as the broader DARIAH community. It is intended to inform the development of future training and education resources, as well as facilitate connections among DARIAH communities with similar training needs.

¹ This report identifies and documents the skills, tools, and knowledge required to achieve a broad range of goals within the web archiving lifecycle and to explore the challenges for participation in web archive research. [The report is available through the WARCnet project.](#)

2. Survey on PhD training needs

Description of the survey

A fundamental aspect of our project involved creating and administering a survey aimed at PhD students from diverse backgrounds and disciplines who were either currently using or considering using Digital Humanities methods for their research. The survey sought to determine the extent of their familiarity with various methods, workflows, and tools, as well as their intentions behind using them.

The first section of the survey gathered general information about the participants, such as age, gender, disciplinary and national background, languages spoken, and their current stage in the PhD program. This data was essential to understand the responses better and identify potential correlations.

The central part of the survey focused on the participants' DH skills and objectives for using digital methods. Specifically, we inquired about their experience levels with DH workflows, including using existing software, finding suitable tools, and accessing training materials. Additionally, we wanted to learn about their capabilities in developing software or training materials for other students and researchers. Another aspect of this part of the survey was to identify the students' training needs and the preferred formats for learning. We provided the following options: (1) an overview of tools available for a subject area, (2) a curated catalogue of available tools, (3) a workshop to introduce a specific tool, and (4) written or recorded tutorials.

Next, we aimed to gather information on specific DH tools with which the PhD researchers were familiar, both within DARIAH (SSH Open Marketplace, Textgrid, DariaTeach, Geo-Browser, Topicexplorer) and outside of it (Palladio, Gephi, MaxQDA, OpenRefine, TEI Publisher, Cytoscape, stylo, Voyant tools, Protégé, StoryMapJS, OCR tools). We carefully selected a diverse range of tools to represent the various applications in the field of DH.

The final part of the survey focused on understanding the potential role DARIAH could play in supporting DH projects and facilitating the acquisition of new skills. We asked participants about their specific use of DARIAH tools and how they accessed information on tools and services relevant to their needs in their day-to-day work. This included questions about whether they utilized services like the marketplace, newsletters, podcasts, or relied on search engines, recommendations from colleagues, or participated in specifically organized workshops.

Survey results

The online survey was active from November 2022 until April 2023. The survey was distributed through DARIAH social media channels, newsletters as well as professional networks of the three chairs. The survey saw a total of 39 completed responses and 34 incomplete responses. Only complete responses were used for the purpose of this report. The survey contained three sections of questions: Consent (including interest in the workshop), demographics, and general knowledge of DH-related tools as well as common ways in which students seek information about new tools and workflows. Except for questions in the consent section, all questions were skippable and in some cases allowed participants to answer using free text fields. The following results focus on the demographics and knowledge of tools of the participants.

Age

Please select the year you were born

The oldest participant was born in 1958, while the youngest participants were born in 1999. It is not surprising to see that the cohort of PhD students is mostly younger than 35 years of age. What is remarkable is a sizable cohort of PhD students over 35 who took part in this survey. Given this age distribution, a possible avenue for further research could be the age distribution of respondents in relation to specific training needs.

Gender

Please indicate the gender you identify as

The survey was not aimed at any specific gender, nor was it advertised using any gender-specific channels. However, the survey saw a majority of female respondents. The discrepancy between the amount of responses received can not be explained by the study design alone, while it is generally observed that women are more likely than men to respond to survey invitations.²

Discipline/Faculty

What is your main discipline or faculty?

² See Becker, Rolf. 2017. "Gender and Survey Participation. An Event History Analysis of the Gender Effects of Survey Participation in a Probability-Based Multi-Wave Panel Study with a Sequential Mixed-Mode Design." *Methods data* (July): 29 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.12758/MDA.2021.08>.

Respondents were asked to identify their main discipline or faculty. This question allowed for free text answers as well as combinations of answers. In the free text, the following answers were given by respondents:

- Art history (2)
- Media Studies
- Kommunikations- und Medienwissenschaft
- Musicology
- Archeology
- Latin Studies
- Human Ecology
- Cinema Studies
- Information Studies

The distribution of answers shows a clear focus on humanities faculties, with only one respondent from Information Sciences and no respondents from Computer Science or similar backgrounds. History and Digital Humanities were the two most common faculties for survey participants.

Location

What country is your home institution based in?

Regarding participants' home institution, the survey saw a clear majority of German institutions, with all other mentioned countries sharing the remaining 50%. Combining the German-speaking countries (including Austria and Switzerland), more than half of respondents' home institutions were based in a German-speaking country.

While DARIAH operates on a European level, and while the survey's distribution was aimed at European participants, we decided not to exclude participants based on their home institution.

Language

Participants were asked to identify the (primary) language their degree program was in.

What language is your PhD program in?

Here, despite the large group of participants from institutions in German-speaking countries, English is the most commonly used language in participants' degree programs. 37.3% of participants are enrolled in degrees taught in German, and around 20% are enrolled in programs taught in other European languages. One participant's program was taught in Hindi, Urdu and Bengali.

Year

Regarding participants' progress in their degree program, a majority of participants are in their first year of the PhD program.

What year of your PhD program are you currently in?

The question did not account for full- or part-time students. Using the four-year-degree model as a reference, around 75% of the participants were within the regular degree duration. Most participants were in the first year of their degree, followed by participants in the second year of their degree. Of the participants who answered "Other", one was in the seventh year, and one answered "final year".

The demographic section shows that most of the participants were female first-year PhD students from German-speaking countries. Degree programs were commonly in Humanities or Digital Humanities subjects, taught in German and/or English. Most participants were younger than 35 years.

DH Tools Knowledge and Needs

Overall goals

Participants were asked to name the general goals when working with or engaging with DH methodology. Participants could select more than one answer and use the free text field.

What are your goals when working with DH methods?

Of the five predefined answers, the two *use* answers (Learn how to (better) use common DH tools, Use DH tools for discipline-specific workflows) were chosen most often. The two answers relating to finding tools (Find common DH tools for my discipline, Adapt new DH tools for use in my discipline) both were chosen by 20 participants. The answer “Develop new DH tools” was chosen by nine participants. Relating to the age and degree stage of participants, most participants were interested in finding and working with existing tools.

Current Knowledge

What is your current knowledge of DH tools and methodology?

Participants were asked to subjectively rate their own experience with DH tools and methodology relevant to their subject area. The result shows an even distribution of participants who rated themselves as 2,3 or 4 out of 5, with 10% of participants saying they

have very high knowledge of current DH tools and methodology and 15% saying they have very low knowledge.

Participants were further asked to evaluate their own experience using existing software as part of their research progress.

Do you have experience using existing software for research?

This question was designed to be more specifically targeted at the use of software rather than the knowledge about tools. In the results, the answers “No experience”, “A little experience” and “Some experience” received 28.2%, 30.8% and 25.6% respectively. This shows a group of 28% of PhD students who state they have no experience in using existing software for research purposes. While the self-evaluations are subjective, the answers to this question show a low level of experience regarding existing tools amongst PhD students.

The following questions specify the level of experience in more detail. Regarding four scenarios, participants were asked to subjectively rate their level of experience. The scenarios were:

- Q1: Finding the appropriate tool/software for my research
- Q2: Finding relevant training material
- Q3: Developing software for research
- Q4: Developing training material

How would you rate your experience with the following:

The results show that for Q1, most participants reported some experience in finding appropriate tools for research, followed by a group of participants with little experience. Regarding Q2, participants reported high to medium levels of experience in finding relevant training materials. Q3 and Q4, both referring to the development of tools and training material, saw over 50% of participants without any experience.

Training formats

How useful would you find the following:

Participants were asked to evaluate the perceived usefulness of four different training formats:

Q1: An overview of tools available for a subject area

Q2: A curated catalogue of available tools

Q3: A workshop to introduce one specific tool

Q4: Written or recorded tutorials

All four formats saw high levels of approval from respondents, especially the format Q1 was described as very useful. No format was described as likely to be not useful to participants.

Familiarity with existing tools and services

How familiar are you with this tool/service:

Participants were asked to describe their level of familiarity with the following tools:

Q1: Textgrid

Q2: SSH Open Marketplace

Q3: DariahTeach

Q4: Topicexplorer

Q5: Geoexplorer

All tools saw low levels of familiarity amongst respondents. Textgrid, as the best-known tool in this selection, was still unknown to 60% of respondents. There was no noticeable difference between the knowledge about tools (Textgrid, Topicexplorer, Geoexplorer) and services such as SSH Open Marketplace and DariahTeach. These low levels of familiarity with all presented tools and services indicate that PhD students are generally unaware of generic DH tools - this may also be related to their discipline - as well as content aggregators.

Asking participants about their familiarity with more general-use tools produces a similar result:

How familiar are you with the following tool:

Q1: Palladio Stanford

Q2: MaxQDA

Q3: TEI Publisher

Q4: OpenRefine

Q5: Cyptoscape

Q6: Voyant Tools

While these tools are better known amongst participants than DH-specific tools, only Voyant tools achieved more than 50% familiarity among participants. Where participants were familiar with a tool, their familiarity was usually low to medium.

Use of DARIAH tools

Participants were asked to name the DARIAH-provided tools they currently use.

What DARIAH tools do you currently use?

Relating to the previous questions, this question confirmed that most participants are not regular users of DARIAH tools. The two most commonly used tools were Textgrid and Topicexplorer. Three users mentioned SSH Open Marketplace, while DariahTeach was used by one respondent.

Searching and Finding new Tools

For the final question, participants were asked how they usually become aware of or find new tools.

How do you normally find tools and services relevant to your work?

The answers show that search engines and recommendations are the most important source of information for participants. Workshops and newsletters were also mentioned as information sources. Academic publications were mentioned twice in the free text section, content aggregators were not mentioned.

Discussion

The demographics of this survey showed a cohort of PhD students mostly at the beginning of their programs. These students are primarily interested in learning about tools and services related to their humanities discipline. Generally, the participants indicated non-technical backgrounds and low awareness of both relevant tools and training or information providers. While all proposed information formats were well received by participants, the results also showed that more formal information-provision systems such as SSH Open Marketplace were not well known.

Following from the survey results, recommendations regarding training needs include:

- Familiarity with tools and information services is generally low. Participants expressed interest in learning about commonly used tools for a humanities subject area.
- Participants learn about new tools most often through less formal channels. Tool and service providers should increase their public profile to increase visibility.
- Training should be aimed at low to medium levels of expertise, English language content will reach the majority of participants.

Following the survey, participants were invited to express their interest in joining an in-person workshop. During this workshop, participants formed focus groups to evaluate different training formats.

3. Focus group workshop

Following our survey about PhD students working with DH tools and DARIAH communities, we organized a two-day workshop in Mainz, Germany, for in-person focus group interviews and joint evaluation of existing training material related to DH studies and work. The workshop took place in the Akademie der Wissenschaften Mainz (The Class of Mathematics and Natural Sciences) in Mainz, Germany, from February 2nd to February 3rd.

In the selection process for the workshop, we considered various disciplines and different levels of expertise of the interviewees as well as their availability and willingness to attend the workshop. With in-person interviews we wanted to develop a more complete picture of the training needs of researchers in this phase of their career.

A total of 9 people attended the workshop: from the Czech Republic (1), Ireland (2), Luxembourg (1), Slovenia (1), and Germany (4). 5 of them were participating in the in-person interviews. The majority (4) are in their first year of a PhD program and one of

them is in the 6th year of the PhD program. One of them rated their current knowledge of DH tools and methodology as very low, feeling very unfamiliar with available tools and methods. Two of the participants rated their current knowledge of DH tools as low, being aware of some tools and methods, one rated their knowledge as medium, somewhat familiar, and one as high, quite knowledgeable about current DH tools and methods. One of the participants said they had no experience with using existing software as part of their research (SPSS, Quant software, anything above reference management), one has some experience and others had a little experience with existing software. None of them was familiar with or used SSH Open Marketplace or DARIAH Teach before the workshop.

We started the workshop with a discussion about the questionnaire results and DH Training needs – what are some of the best practices, Dos and Don'ts? We continued with evaluation and personal experience with training offers and concluded with a discussion: Which services should DARIAH and Community Engagement Working Group provide?

Best practices, Dos and Don'ts: Training Needs Assessment

Participants were invited to identify their training needs and potential solutions. During the assessment, participants were given a list of training needs encompassing various aspects of research, communication, career development, teaching and more. They were encouraged to evaluate the provided list or think about their own training needs and express their priorities based on personal experiences and aspirations.

List of provided training needs:

Research & knowledge skills (effective research processes)

- Finding & managing info
- Critical & creative thinking
- Research methods & methodologies

Communication (research impact)

- Presenting & public speaking
- Publishing
- Platforms for dissemination

Collaboration (engagement)

- Networking
- Teamwork
- Supervision, mentoring

Career development (positive career outcomes)

- Career opportunities
- Career planning

- Teaching & learning
- Funding opportunities
- Motivation

The results: Evaluation of DARIAH and other DH tools and training offers

The analysis of participants' responses unveiled several prominent training requirements. These participants articulated a wide range of needs aimed at enhancing their research capabilities and overall productivity. They emphasized the importance of effective research processes to optimize their work and efficiently manage information. Additionally, there was a strong demand for the development of critical and creative thinking skills, fostering innovative approaches to address research challenges. Participants recognized the significance of effective communication to increase the impact of their research findings.

Training in collaboration and networking emerged as crucial to fostering productive research partnerships. Moreover, participants highlighted the value of teamwork, supervision, and mentoring to create a positive and supportive research environment.

Furthermore, participants expressed keen interest in learning about funding opportunities to support their research projects. Lastly, they emphasized the need for training to maintain motivation and resilience throughout their academic journey.

In addition to assessing the provided training needs, participants proffered potential solutions to bridge the identified gaps. They recommended organizing workshops and seminars concentrating on specific research subjects. Participants suggested granting access to online resources and webinars encompassing various training topics. The notion of arranging networking events and PhD conferences to facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange within the research community was put forth.

The training needs assessment yielded insightful results, highlighting the specific requirements of participants in research, career development, and other related areas. Based on the identified needs and potential solutions, designing comprehensive and targeted training programs can empower PhD students, enhance their skills, and foster their professional growth and success. Implementation of some of these solutions can offer stronger support to their research communities and ensure a more enriching and productive academic journey for them.

During the evaluation session, the participants were tasked with assessing the current teaching and training materials available for students interested in Digital Humanities tools, methods and approaches. Their primary focus was to discern the strengths and weaknesses of these resources. The participants examined the materials, noting what aspects they found beneficial and valuable. Additionally, they were asked to identify any shortcomings or gaps in the content and offer suggestions on potential improvements. They shared their thoughts on what was lacking, what could be done better, and the information they found most useful

was actively sought, encouraging a comprehensive and constructive assessment of the existing resources.

DARIAH Teach

#dariahTeach is a platform for Open Educational Resources (OER) for Digital Arts and Humanities educators and students, but also beyond this aiming at Higher Education across a spectrum of disciplines, at teachers and trainers engaged in the digital transformation of programme content and learning methods. Content on #dariahTeach is designed to be asynchronously accessed by both lone learners, especially those who do not have access to digital arts and humanities teaching and training, as well as educators who can embed content into their own course offerings.³

Positives	Negatives
Immediate availability of course offerings	Lack of clear differentiation between courses
Visually appealing and accessible list of courses	Unclear about the specific knowledge, skills, or benefits offered by each course
Well-structured course content	Missing information on how courses can be interconnected or linked
Video materials to enhance learning experience	Courses are not well-clustered and systemized
Interactive quizzes for assessment and reinforcement of knowledge	Limited course selection
Valuable resource for educators and instructors	
Offers courses in multiple languages	

Participants' evaluation of DARIAH Teach shows several positive features that effectively enhance the learning experience for individuals interested in Digital Arts and Humanities. The immediate availability of course offerings in multiple languages, catering to a diverse audience, visually appealing layout that is easy for learners to navigate, and well-structured course content enriched with video materials and interactive quizzes as a valuable resource for educators are notable strengths. However, the platform also faces challenges in terms of clear course differentiation, interconnection and systemization, as well as a limited course selection. The participants stressed that the training materials do not adequately communicate the specific knowledge and skills that learners can expect to gain from each course. They would appreciate information on how courses can be interconnected or linked to create a cohesive learning journey. With only 15 tutorials offered, the platform's training offer might be considered narrow, limiting the options for learners seeking a broader range of topics. Addressing these issues could significantly improve the overall effectiveness and

³ Source: <https://teach.dariah.eu/local/staticpage/view.php?page=about>, 25. 7. 2023.

appeal of the training offer, making it more attractive to a wider audience of learners and educators.

DARIAH Campus

DARIAH-Campus is both a discovery framework and a hosting platform for DARIAH and DARIAH-affiliated offerings in training and education. The goal of DARIAH-Campus is to widen access to open, inclusive, high-quality learning materials that aim to enhance creativity, skills, technology and knowledge in the digitally-enabled arts and humanities. Within DARIAH-Campus, users can find different types of learning resources, and the captured outputs of face-to-face events run by members of the community.⁴

Positives	Negatives
Provided links to external tools	Unstructured content
Useful courses	Difficult to identify main topics and subtopics
Functions as a search engine	Confusing course titles
Suitable for both bachelor and master students	Insufficient use of relevant keywords
	Limited offer of courses

The user feedback evaluation of DARIAH Teach provided valuable insights into the platform's strengths and areas that require improvement. The positive feedback highlighted the usefulness of links to external tools, broadening the available resources beyond the platform's own content, the high relevance of specific courses like "Python for Topic Modelling" that catered to their specific interests and skill development needs, and the search engine feature. However, the constructive feedback indicated several challenges related to content organization, relevance, and search functionality. Several participants expressed feeling overwhelmed by the lack of clear organization and structure on the platform. The absence of well-defined main topics and subtopics made it challenging for users to navigate through the content effectively. Some participants noted the presence of materials not directly related to Digital Humanities, feeling it diminished the platform's focus and relevance. Participants raised concerns about the inadequate use of relevant keywords, leading to difficulties in understanding the actual content covered and hampering efficient search capabilities. While the platform appeared to have a significant number of courses,

⁴ Source: <https://campus.dariah.eu/docs/about>, 25. 7. 2023.

participants expressed disappointment with the depth of the content upon closer exploration. Addressing these concerns could lead to a broader user engagement with the platform.

Digital Humanities Course Registry

The participants expressed unfamiliarity with the Digital Humanities Course Registry, a curated platform offering a comprehensive overview of the expanding array of teaching activities in the global digital humanities domain.⁵ Developed jointly by the European research infrastructures CLARIN and DARIAH, the platform aims to simplify the process of accessing information about various degree programs.

Positives	Negatives
Good overview of the available study programs	No real transparency about the type of information that can be found (or not found) on the page
Filter possibilities	List not exhaustive, not all universities are included
	Confusion on the type of courses that are in the list
	Language column for the course would be useful

At first glance, the participants were impressed with the concept of having a centralized resource where they could easily find information about potential degree programs. They appreciated the convenience the website offered to students seeking guidance on where to apply. At a second glance, however, the usefulness of the page was limited, as the list of course types is not always systematic. An indication of the course language would be considered particularly helpful.

Parthenos

The Parthenos training suite offers comprehensive training modules and resources in the field of digital humanities, with a specific emphasis on research infrastructures.⁶ These

⁵ Source: <https://dhcr.clarin-dariah.eu/>, 25. 7. 2023.

⁶ Source: <https://training.parthenos-project.eu/>, 25. 7. 2023.

modules cater to both trainers seeking to incorporate these methods into their courses and individuals interested in self-paced learning.

Positives	Negatives
Good webpage	The notion of research infrastructure remains unclear
Systematic and consecutive courses	Who is the targeted audience?
A variety of training modules	

Participants valued the well-organized webpage, which follows a systematic approach, with modules building upon one another. However, a drawback is the lack of clarity regarding the courses offered and the precise definition of "research infrastructure." The current presentation of the offerings appears somewhat arbitrary, and the intended audience for these courses remains unclear.

To enhance the user experience, the website could provide clearer information about the course content and learning objectives. Additionally, defining the target audience for each module would help potential learners identify the most relevant courses for their needs. By addressing these areas of improvement, the Parthenos training suite could provide an even more effective and user-friendly learning platform.

SSH open marketplace

The project aims to provide a full-fledged Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for users of SSH data. The focus of the project is determined by the goal to further the innovation of infrastructural support for digital scholarship, to stimulate multidisciplinary collaboration across the various subfields of SSH and beyond, and to increase the potential for societal impact.

Positives	Negatives
Useful courses, training materials, and tools	Lack of awareness about the existence of this platform among the participants
Efficient keyword-based search functionality	
Access to external websites	

The feedback from participants revealed several positive aspects of the SSH open marketplace platform, including its useful courses, comprehensive training materials and valuable tools, efficient search functionality that allowed users to discover relevant materials, including content they might not have known they were looking for, and access to external resources, further enriching the learning experience. However, a critical issue emerged from the evaluation, indicating that the platform suffers from a lack of awareness among potential users.

ForTEXT

ForTEXT offers beginner-friendly method descriptions, text collections and tools – from digitization to digital annotation to digitally supported interpretation and visualization of literature. It also provides materials for self-study and for teaching digital text analysis methods at universities and schools. ForTEXT is usable for humanities scholars without previous technical knowledge and provides a whole suite of tools and digital methods for text analysis that can be directly combined with each other.⁷

Positives	Negatives
Specific and focused content	Available only in German
Interactive and graphic elements	
Information about the current state of the tool, including details on discontinued projects	
Usefulness of each tool in specific areas of study	

The evaluation of the ForTEXT unveiled several positive aspects, including its specific and focused content, interactive elements that facilitate dynamic learning and the usefulness of each tool. Participants appreciated the fact that it provides information about the current state of the tool, including details on discontinued projects, and offers insights into the specific areas where each tool is useful, allowing them to identify its relevance to their field of study. A significant drawback observed was that the platform is exclusively available in the German language. This limitation restricts access for non-German speakers and hinders its reach to a more diverse audience.

⁷ Source: <https://fortext.net/ueber-fortext>, 25. 7. 2023.

Programming historian

The Programming Historian is a website providing peer-reviewed tutorials tailored for beginners, offering a diverse array of digital tools, techniques, and workflows to enhance research and teaching experiences.⁸ The website is maintained by a dedicated volunteer community that actively promotes inclusivity and diversity among editors, writers, and readers. The tutorials are thoughtfully organized, aligning with different stages of the research process and covering a wide range of general topics. Users can easily filter lessons based on specific categories.

Positives	Negatives
well organised	
easy to use	
multilingual	
peer-reviewed	

Although most participants were previously unaware of the website, they found it to be highly beneficial and well-structured. Its user-friendly interface and comprehensive content left a positive impression on them.

4. What should CE WG & DARIAH provide?

During the concluding segment of the workshop, we engaged in a fruitful discussion about the potential contributions of the WG Community Engagement and DARIAH as a whole in facilitating the search for training opportunities for PhD students. We encouraged participants to share their ideas regarding specific services that could be offered to address this need.

A consensus emerged among the participants that finding appropriate information was challenging due to the overwhelming presence of numerous websites, all offering similar but not identical information. Additionally, they pointed out that often, expected links to further

⁸ Source: <https://programminghistorian.org/>, 25. 7. 2023.

resources were missing. To tackle this issue, participants agreed that having consolidated information on tools and resources available on department websites would be immensely beneficial.

The WG Community Engagement could play a vital role in achieving this by providing research centres and departments with a standardized bundle of information. By targeting department mailing lists, they could effectively disseminate relevant information. The WG's responsibility would entail compiling comprehensive details about DARIAH services, events, and other valuable resources, ensuring that this information reaches the DH departments.

As a secondary outcome, participants envisioned the creation of a dedicated website to archive and make these resources easily accessible. In response to their needs, they also emphasized the importance of assessments of various tools and software, which would assist them in making informed decisions for their research. They pointed to the German website forText as a model for this approach.

Regarding learning opportunities, participants expressed a strong preference for concrete workshops offered in small groups, akin to those available during DH conferences. Specific areas of demand included courses on text analysis tools and visualization methods. Furthermore, participants were eager to gain insights into repositories and sought regular hands-on beginner courses in Python for the DH.

Lastly, PhD students sought a secure and supportive space where they could freely discuss workflows and methods with their peers without the interference of supervisors or superiors. They proposed the establishment of a platform where individuals could share their research experiences, discuss PhD-related challenges and solutions, and exchange knowledge and skills with like-minded peers.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

The information landscape for PhD students can be marked by an ambivalence of experiencing information overload while facing challenges in finding the right information tailored to their specific needs. There is a need for a comprehensive approach that goes beyond individual research projects or research infrastructures, ensuring information is bundled and easily accessible. Among the various resources available, websites offering well-defined tutorials on specific workflows and evaluation of tools are highly appreciated by students.

Additionally, there is a crucial requirement for an infrastructure dedicated explicitly to supporting doctoral students, recognizing their occasional uncertainties about their own skills and expertise. Providing a supportive platform for their unique needs can greatly enhance their research progress. One concern of the WG Community Engagement could therefore be to collect targeted information for beginners and newcomers to DH and to act as a point of contact.

By effectively promoting and communicating the existence of these training opportunities, PhD students would make the most of the existing DH tools and resources. Collaboration,

networking, teamwork, and mentoring were recognized as essential for creating a positive and supportive research environment. Additionally, providing access to funding opportunities and offering training to maintain motivation throughout their academic journey were emphasized. In contrast, the services offered by DARIAH are not well-known among PhD students and are perceived as not always easily accessible, sometimes appearing random. They find the structure of DARIAH confusing, and it lacks a clearly defined target audience. An easy-to-implement recommendation could therefore be the formulation of a concrete target group for training offers.

Addressing the diverse training needs identified by the participants of our 2-day workshop is crucial for empowering PhD students, enhancing their research capabilities, and fostering their professional growth. The analysis highlights the significance of expanding user engagement with the available training offers and materials, with a primary emphasis on ensuring that PhD students are well-informed and aware of these resources. Furthermore, the PhD students need to be given the opportunity to meet in person among themselves.

To bridge the identified gaps, future work should continue to focus on designing comprehensive and targeted training programs, organizing workshops and seminars on specific research topics, providing online resources and webinars, and facilitating networking events and conferences. A recommendation to DARIAH is therefore to invest in smaller, targeted in-person meetings for early career researchers. In addition to identifying the importance of expanding user engagement, it becomes evident that significant efforts need to be invested in effectively promoting and communicating the existence of these training opportunities.